

Deterministic and non-deterministic formulations for home energy optimization to support new energy services

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Abstract: Home energy management systems (HEMS) are becoming important platforms and are set to enable consumers to make use of the flexibility of their energy consumption. The energy use in domestic buildings can be optimized considering the existing flexible loads and microgeneration and at the same time consider the preferences and configurations of the end-users. The continuous evolution of HEMS in including new functionalities and their integration in cost-effective computational platforms is leading to the use of different optimization formulations to produce efficient algorithms capable of producing fast solutions for increasingly complex systems. The work presented in this paper focuses on the exploitation of non-deterministic optimization algorithms such as genetic algorithms and cross-entropy as suitable alternatives to traditional formulations based on mixed integer linear programming formulations. Different scenarios are presented, based on several EU contexts, with the modelling of the different energy elements, local load and production, to be employed in real HEMS capable of outputting feasible, understandable and useful schedules, of the existing portfolio of automated and/or manual devices and systems. The performance of the different formulations is presented through several simulations and real testing that validated the algorithms capability to find optimized solutions.

1 Notation

Subscripts

t	time (h)
i	period i for the appliance use
θ	temperature restriction
PL	power cap restriction
D	deferrable restriction

Superscripts

D	deferrable appliances
T	thermal appliances
PV	photovoltaic
uL	uncontrollable loads
CP	contracted power

Variables/Constants

n_{steps}	number of control periods
n	number of appliances
dt	appliance duration of operation (h)
P	power of appliance (kW)
x	binary variable-condition
λ	algorithm penalty
C	energy cost (€/kWh)
θ	temperature (°C)
θ_e	exterior temperature (°C)
C	thermal capacity (kWh/°C)
R	thermal resistance (°C/kW)
η	coefficient of performance
S	real-value function
γ	threshold or level parameter
γ^*	minimum limit
\mathbf{x}	values in state space
\mathbf{x}^*	minimizer
TC	total cost of all appliances

2 Introduction

Electric power systems have undergone, in recent years, significant changes due to the progressive integration of distributed energy resources, namely, in low voltage systems. From the beginning of the 21st century, there has been a significant increase in distributed renewable energy sources, creating the need to develop more advanced monitoring models and new functionalities capable of mitigating the technical impacts from the integration of distributed energy resources while exploiting their benefits for the distribution network planning and operation.

The transition to a more flexible distribution system, which requires more observability, controllability and efficiency, has led to the definition of the smart grid concept [1]. This new paradigm promotes a bidirectional flow of electricity and communication between consumers and suppliers, through the deployment of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) throughout the different segments of the grid, most notably in the distribution. Consumers can now be active players with the possibility to manage their consumption and to implement intelligent control actions with the objective of reducing energy costs, reducing peaks, levelling energy consumption, and integrating local renewable generation.

Given the recent advances in ICT and building automation, now there are tools for the consumer to optimize its energy use. In fact, great attention is now being given to Home Energy Management Systems (HEMS). These systems are designed to optimize energy consumption and increase energy efficiency for residential users. It is an interactive platform that allows the scheduling of the different devices and systems in a household towards the reduction of energy costs as well as CO₂ emissions. For domestic users, HEMS are an important decision support tool for the adoption of new energy services by handling all of the relevant contextual information regarding price tariffs, the characteristics of the devices and systems, along with the preferences of the user, and carry out the necessary automation actions, in the most seamless way, to ensure the optimal energy use. In addition,

this platform is also sought to induce benefits to the user, such as a better understanding of energy use, discriminated information about energy use (e.g., per appliance, per room, etc.), or insights into problematic equipment (e.g., fault detection, efficiency reduction due to aging, etc.).

From the retailers perspective, HEMS can also provide relevant information particularly regarding the flexibility of electricity use. This can be performed considering the likelihood of specific loads being activated at different periods of time, which in an aggregated fashion can allow a more stable market participation either in retail and ancillary services markets.

Several studies have already explored the benefits of optimization models in the context of power management within households. Some, have already shown real results on demonstrators of domestic consumers. For example, a classical approach was made for the AnyPLACE [2] platform algorithm, in order to achieve cost savings and maximize photovoltaic (PV) self-consumption. However, the present results demonstrate that it is not always possible to find an optimal solution in a suitable time length for practical applications, especially given the growing complexity of domestic scenarios. This means that heuristic optimization techniques may be exploited to provide HEMS, which have limited computational capabilities, a way of producing fast solutions (optimal and sub-optimal).

With the aim of tackling these challenges, this paper presents a set of heuristic formulations for adaptable energy optimization algorithms capable of outputting feasible, understandable and useful actions for the activation of the existing portfolio of flexible devices in a household. For that purpose a traditional Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) formulation was used, from a set of **previous works**. It acted as basis against which Genetic Algorithms (GA) and the Cross-Entropy (CE) formulations were compared to, with the purpose of evaluating the possibility of solving the same problem in a more efficient way, specifically considering fast sub-optimal results.

In section 3 is presented the state of the art and the related work within the scope of the work presented in this paper. Section 4 introduces the energy management methodology that is used to produce optimized schedules of appliances and microgeneration systems for the next day. Section 5 presents the algorithms formulations that were implemented and evaluated in this paper. In section 6 a set of scenarios, likely to be found in households, is presented and where energy optimization procedures are expected to be used. In section 7 the global results are presented and discussed. The main conclusions from the work presented in this paper are drawn in 8 along with some **considerations for future work**.

3 State of the art

3.1 Demand Response

Demand response (DR) is a concept that dates back to several decades ago with the first automated implementations made in the 1970s through the use of radio and ripple control systems to manage high-consumption devices such as air conditioning and water heating systems [3].

With the growing amount of distributed energy resources, specially PV in the distribution grids, the concept of DR has evolved beyond the use of peak shaving shaving techniques. Current programs are potentially capable of providing services with direct benefits to the distribution network, reflecting the transformation of demand response from a way to shave peak demand to an increasingly valuable tool to manage the modern grid.

The flexibility on the demand side, namely the ability to increase or decrease the load over a given period of time [4], can allow consumers to participate in a wider set of energy

services. The supporting computation, automation and communication functionalities in residential buildings is provided the HEMS.

3.2 Energy Management Schemes

Energy management schemes can be based on dynamic or time-of-use tariffs to encourage consumers to run their devices out of peak hours and benefit from lower prices. It is also possible to develop schemes considering PV production. Apart from cost savings, such schemes can also maximize the remuneration associated with self-consumption.

The effectiveness of energy management schemes is deeply related to the self-consumption regulation. In countries, such as Germany and Portugal, policies have been devised to encourage instant consumption when the renewable resource is available. Recent legislation in Portugal [5] ended the previously feed-in tariff and consequently lower remuneration for PV generation. This led to a reduction in the financial gains from PV injecting in the grid, especially considering the electricity consumption prices, which translated into self-consumption being more profitable than injecting power into the grid [6].

3.3 Device Modelling

Effective home energy management requires a preliminary analysis of the household consumption, the characteristics and configurations of existing appliances, as well as the consumption habits. This assessment is fundamental for understanding the overall behavior of the devices, including interdependencies and interaction with other devices. This process can be done based on historical data retrieved from the household or based on default consumption patterns. However, these kind of methods does not offer results with sufficient accuracy, especially when dealing with thermal loads. Thus energy management systems need to be connected to sensors that monitor the energy consumption or allow the user insert related information.

Two different categories of appliances are usually considered in the literature – controllable and non-controllable loads. The latter category can be further distinguished between thermal loads and deferrable loads.

Deferrable loads are appliances that operate on a predefined cycle with a known duration and power consumption. The term deferrable is used since the operation of these type of devices can be shifted along the planning horizon (24h of the next day). Smart deferrable appliances can be remotely controlled and monitored by the HEMS while the manual ones are activated by the user, when requested to, or through the use of smart plugs.

Modelling thermal devices, such as an electrical water heater or an air conditioner, is considerably more complex than deferrable loads. In [7] a thermal process of an Air Conditioner (AC) using a comparison with an Resistor-Capacitor (RC) circuit is presented. The objective of this approach relies on establishing four relations between electrical circuits and the thermal balance inside a room in which and AC device is operating. Similar differential equations are used to characterize other types of thermal loads, namely refrigerators (RF) and Electric Water Heaters (EWH). In case of refrigerators, the thermal model is equivalent to the AC representation. EWH models are very diverse, each one accounting for different constructive characteristics of this type of appliances [8].

3.4 Optimization Algorithms

Optimization methods can be divided into deterministic and non-deterministic (heuristic and meta-heuristic). Deterministic approaches can provide general tools for solving

optimization problems in order to obtain the global optimum or near optimal solution. This approach takes advantage of the mathematical formulation of the problem to generate a sequence of points that converge to the global optimum. Deterministic optimization assumes that perfect information about the cost function is available and uses that information to determine the search direction in a classic manner at every step of the algorithm [9]. In the literature, the most referenced class of optimization problems solved with deterministic methods are Linear Programming (LP) [10–13], and MILP [14–17].

Heuristic approaches can be more flexible and efficient, but the quality of the obtained solution is not guaranteed. Like deterministic optimization methods, there is no single method that works well for all problems. Therefore, structural assumptions - such as limits on the size of the decision and outcome spaces, or convexity - are needed to make problems tractable [18]. Moreover, the probability of finding the global optimum solution is inversely proportional to the size of the problem.

Meta-heuristics, such as GA [19–22], have been successfully applied in solving several classification, decision, simulation and optimization problems. By searching over a large set of feasible solutions, heuristics can find good solutions with reduced computational effort [23–26]. Some known examples of optimization heuristics are the Genetic Algorithms, Particle Swarm Optimization and Simulated Annealing. Lately, some papers have also referenced the use of the Cross Entropy method [27] as a simple, efficient and general method for solving complex estimation and optimization problems. This method offers a generic approach to combinatorial and multi-external optimization and rare event simulation - where very small probabilities are needed to be estimated (e.g., reliability analysis, or performance analysis of telecommunication systems) [28].

3.5 Related Work

Several works in the literature have been exploiting the benefits of optimization models in the context of HEMS. For instance, in [29] an energy management solution that learns and adapts to the residential electricity usage patterns is proposed. The model consists in an adaptive neuro-fuzzy learning algorithm that makes decisions based on peak load, dynamic electricity prices, customer usage patterns and electricity budget, as well as on social and environmental factors and available PV production. The learning of this algorithm is implemented in two stages. The first is a neural network that provides the learning machine that permits to identify the unknown or the changing power plant and the latter is a fuzzification component that compensates the uncertainties or inaccuracies related to the plant or the environment.

In [30] and [31] a multi-scale multi-stage stochastic optimization model is presented for HEMS formulated as a Model Predictive Control algorithm that minimizes costs and peak-power constraints. The model includes plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEV) charging, thermal dynamics, temperature measurement and real-time pricing signals. In both works, a partition of the energy management into slow and fast time scales is made to reduce computation complexity.

In [32] a stochastic dynamic programming framework is proposed for the optimal management of a smart home with Plug-in Electric Vehicle (PEV) energy storage. The model aims to minimize electricity ratepayer cost while satisfying home power demand and PEV charging requirements.

In [33] a combination of a GA with LP is proposed to reduce the electricity consumption costs of a smart home. Besides the energy scheduling problem, their study also includes the modelling of the battery of a PEV and the economic and technical constraints for PV production, thereby

resulting in a non-linear, time-varying and stochastic optimization problem. Their approach separates the discrete variables from the continuous variables by addressing the non-linearity of the problem with the GA (discrete) and boosting the search for the global optimum with LP (continuous).

In [34] an appliance's commitment algorithm is presented that schedules thermostatically controlled household loads based on price and consumption forecasts. The model considers user's comfort settings to meet an optimization objective such as minimum payment or maximum comfort. The EWH is considered, being its operation over the scheduling time horizon predicted by the physical model. The author transforms the user's comfort parameters in a set of linear constraints and use a linear sequential optimization multiloop algorithm to solve the appliances commitment problem based on price and consumption forecasts.

In [35] an optimal and automatic residential electricity consumption scheduling framework was developed based on simple LP computations. The model aims to achieve a trade-off between minimizing the payment and minimizing the waiting time for the operation of each household appliance based on the needs declared by users. A price prediction filter is used to improve the algorithm results.

In [36] a GA and a polynomial function-based solution is proposed. The objective is to minimize the combination of generation cost and the inconvenience caused to the customer. The combination of costs are composed by capital cost that depends on the power rating of generating unit, maintenance cost which depends on power rating and/or energy generated and operating cost that depend on the fuel cost. The boiler is modeled as 3rd degree polynomial assuming there is no loads with discontinuous inconvenience function.

A multiobjective GA is used in [37] to address the optimization problem in smart grid by shifting the controllable devices to start working at appropriate time. When solving a multiobjective optimization problem, more than one objective is considered simultaneously. To compare the chromosomes a Pareto dominance is used. The target is to find the Pareto Optimal, which is a set of solutions which cannot be dominated by any other solutions.

4 Energy Management Methodology

4.1 Problem Description

The methodology presented in this work includes the internal inputs related to the home domain and the external inputs received from service providers that are interested in shaping the energy demand of certain households. The internal inputs comprise the operation of appliances according to a specific set of preferences and configurations, and the way users manage these devices. These inputs are used to determine the flexibility of the energy use in each household. In addition, the behaviour of the appliances and their influence on the end-user's consumption is carried out to identify the ones more suitable to be rescheduled.

4.2 Energy Management

4.2.1 Controllable Appliances: As previously mentioned, two different types of controllable appliances were considered: deferrable and thermal appliances.

The deferrable device model is based on three parameters: power (kW), duration (h) and number of times to be activated during the day. The number of timeframes for the appliance is determined according to how many times the appliance operates. For example, if the appliance only operates once, then there is only one timeframe; if it operates four times, four timeframes are considered. Within each timeframe it is possible to define a time interval for operation, during which the control method will decide the best time for activation.

Some important points must be considered concerning timeframes:

- If there is only one timeframe, the user can define an interval for the operation (e.g., between [9 am - 6 pm]) or an interval to exclude operation (e.g., [18 am - 11 pm] meaning that it can operate between [0 am - 11 am], cannot operate between [11 am - 6 pm], and can operate again between [6 pm - 12 pm]);
- If there is more than one timeframe, then an interval to exclude operation cannot be defined. In addition, the starting time of the next operation cannot overlap the previous one (e.g., two timeframes: if the first one has a deadline at 9 am, then the second only can start after 9 am, including)

In terms of algorithm, this type of appliances is the only one that can be freely added by the user, since only three parameters are required.

The modelling approach adopted for thermal devices modelling is based on the Physically-Based Load Models (PBLM) developed in [8]. PBLMs for thermal loads are based on energy balances that occur inside a thermal chamber, which can be a room – in the case of space heating devices –, a RF cavity or the cylinder for the hot water. Two different models are considered, one for the AC and another for the EWH. Each model is detailed in its respective sub-section.

Note that the model for the AC can also be applied to the RF. However this appliance was not considered in this study since the RF have tight limits in terms of temperature and fast variations when powered having little impact in the cost minimization. Moreover, these devices consume less power when compared to the other appliances and are currently being designed to be as efficient as possible.

4.2.2 User Preferences: The preferences set by the users in an HEMS platform can be quite complex raising additional challenges in the definition of an optimal schedule for the following day. In order to overcome these challenges, the system was designed to consider several possible scheduling parameters that can be modified by the user according to his preferences and appliances type. The user preferences are treated as restrictions in the formulation of the cost minimization problem, and as such they need to be carefully considered to avoid making the problem unfeasible. For deferrable appliances, the user has the possibility to choose one or more deadlines, depending how many times the appliance is going to work that day, with a maximum operation horizon of 24h. A time window is available between the configuration time and the deadline, during which the control method can choose the optimal start time. If the appliances are manual with no possibility of remote control, then the user must indicate a time interval in which the appliance can be connected manually. For thermal appliances, the consumer can set his comfort requirements such as the desired hot water temperature and the usual number of baths per period, for the following day (e.g. “2 baths @ 7:00 am and 1 bath @ 8:00 pm”). The user may impose further restrictions to the optimization problem by adding a power cap or contracted power limits. However, this introduces additional challenges requiring a more extensive characterization of the power consumption baseline and of the inflexible loads through direct measurement or estimation.

4.2.3 External Interaction: The energy management system is capable of incorporating functions to deal with external information as well. This information includes tariff publishing (load and generation) and other online services that can provide local forecasts for the day-ahead. Hence, three sets of data are included in the algorithm, namely: (i) price tariffs from energy providers and remuneration for the PV production injected into the grid; (ii) temperature for the next day; (iii) PV forecast, that includes the expected PV production.

4.2.4 Optimization Objectives: The formulation of the optimization problem depends on goal to be achieved. Among the wide diversity of optimization criteria for an energy management system, the cost is probably the most appealing one as it focuses on finding a less expenditures for the energy use. If price discrimination follows an efficiency goal from the grid perspective, then the participants will be participating in a DR program as well.

Note that the objective function still consists in minimizing the electricity costs even if PV is considered for the optimal day-ahead scheduling. In this case, the remuneration associated with PV based self-consumption for the day-ahead operation is computed based on the expected PV generation and the domestic inflexible load.

4.3 HEMS Architecture

The implementation of the energy management system aforementioned was firstly achieved in the AnyPLACE H2020 project that specified the functional, technical and technological requirements of such a solution. The main outcome was a SW and HW platform capable of interconnecting with other devices and systems. This platform is currently being upgraded with new features and a more dynamic and easy-to-use interface. It will also be tested in a real demonstrator of the Integrid H2020 project in Portugal and Sweden.

The energy management system developed is capable of storing the configuration and comfort preferences of users and with it produce optimal schedules of appliances (legacy and smart) for the following day. It is a highly customizable platform that incorporate functionalities from other existing systems as well as innovative ones related with the energy management purpose. The SW modules were designed, implemented and embedded into a Raspberry PI 3 computation core to produce a cost effective solution that is flexible and adaptable to different contexts.

5 Optimization Tools

As explained in the previous section, the computational capacity required at the HEMS processing unit to run this optimization problem may be significant, especially with the growth of the problem size due to time parameters or the number of devices. For example, the calculation of the schedule for the 24 hours ahead considering 15 minutes time step result in 96 periods. Therefore, it is necessary to find optimization methods that provide reliable results in a useful time for the user and can be implemented in the computational platforms presented in the previous section.

This chapter presents the methodologies used for the optimization behind the energy scheduling problem as well as the general architecture of the algorithms. Two different approaches are presented – deterministic and non deterministic.

5.1 Deterministic

A deterministic optimization method was implemented in order to achieve cost savings and maximize PV self-consumption. The optimization criteria for cost savings is performed to minimize the total daily cost and considers dynamic price tariffs, peak-power limit, deferrable appliances with different durations, power consumption and number of activations, as well as the models and external data for thermal appliances.

The multi-period problem is implemented and solved as a scheduling problem using binary variables that represent the decisions of activation of the domestic appliances. The binary decision variables in each period represent the on / off control: 0 and nominal power consumption.

An optimization criteria that can be performed by the HEMS platform, is presented in the objective function (1), where the aim is to find the lowest daily cost for the energy consumed from the grid.

$$\min\left(\sum_{t=0}^{n_{steps}} C_t \cdot \left[\sum_{j=1}^{n^D} \sum_{i=0}^{dt^D} [P_i^j \times x_{t-i}^j] + \sum_{k=1}^{n^T} [P_t^k \times x_t^k]\right]\right) \quad (1)$$

The objective function presented in (2) consists in minimizing the electricity costs, considering the remuneration associated with PV based self-consumption for the day-ahead operation taking into account the expected PV generation and the domestic inflexible load.

$$\min(-C_t^{PV} \times Y_t^+ + C_t \times Y_t^-) \quad (2)$$

Both objective functions can be considered if the house has PV installed. The objective is chosen by the end user regarding his preferences towards a more economic or ecologic house.

Equations 3, 4 and 5 show the necessary constraints formulation in order to enable the application of linear programming techniques to the second objective function. For PV optimization decision variables Y^+ and Y^- were included in order to represent the situation when the PV is higher and lower than the residential consumption, respectively. The binary variable u_t and the large positive constant M is used to impose either/or constraints.

$$Y_t^+ - Y_t^- = P_t^{PV} - P_t^{uL} - P_t^D - P_t^T \quad (3)$$

$$Y_t^+ \leq u_t M \quad (4)$$

$$Y_t^- \leq (1 - u_t) M \quad (5)$$

To develop a realistic model of the problem several constraints have to be considered. Both the comfort level and consumption patterns of the user have to be contemplated. Also, some technical limitations regarding the country's policy could exist and cannot be disregarded.

In fact, there are contracted limitations to the power consumed from the grid, namely for LV consumers. This constraint is considered in equation 6 and introduces additional challenges as it necessary to characterize further, through direct measurement or estimation, the power consumption baseline and the inflexible loads.

$$P_t^{CP} \geq P_t^{uL} + P_t^D + P_t^T \quad (6)$$

For deferrable appliances the user has the possibility to choose one or more deadlines (depending how many times the appliance is going to work that day) with a maximum operation span of 24h. A time window is available between a configuration time and deadline, during which the control method can choose the optimal start time. Hence, for each activation defined by the end user the constraint defined in equation 7 is added per appliance for the available time window.

$$\sum_{t=0}^{Dt_j - dt_j} x_t^D = 1 \quad (7)$$

Regarding the thermal appliances each one is associated to two comfort constraints (maximum and minimum temperature) as well as an equality constraint.

The linearization of these constraints was already developed in other works and the complete explanation can be consulted in [8]. This consists in an abstract representation of appliances physically based load models defined in equation 8 for the air conditioner and in equation 9 for the electric water heater. The integration of these models contains a recurrence relation between the decisions variables, i.e., the consumption in each period depends on the consumption in previous periods.

$$\theta_t = \theta_{t-1} + \frac{\Delta_t}{R \times C} [\theta_{t-1} - \theta_e + \eta \times R \times P] \quad (8)$$

$$\theta_t = \theta_{t-1} + \frac{\Delta_t}{C} [-\alpha(\theta_{t-1} - \theta_e)] - c_p \times v_t(\theta_d - \theta_{in}) + P \quad (9)$$

5.2 Non deterministic

A non deterministic approach was developed with two different methods: GA and CE method. A GA is a well-known probabilistic search algorithm based on the theory of evolution. It relies on the mutation/recombination of solutions and on natural selection to obtain a population of solutions with high fitness. On the other hand, the CE method is a heuristic based on iterated sampling of the state space. Basically, the optimization problem is interpreted as a rare event estimation problem - the so-called associated stochastic problem (ASP). The ASP is solved by an adaptive sampling process that consists on: (i) generation of random samples according to a specified mechanism; (ii) update the parameters of the random mechanism, based on the data, to produce improved samples over the iterations. The main outcome is the construction of a random sequence of degenerate densities that converge probabilistically to the optimal (or near optimal) solution.

The idea for both heuristics is the creation of a single objective function to be minimized, that includes the influence of all the variables in the problem. This function can be expressed as in Eq.10 and will be applied to determine a single performance per sample. The function benefits the samples that minimize the total cost of operation and comply at the same time with temperature and power limit constraints. The fourth element (λ_D) is only added to the equation when using the CE method, since it is necessary a penalization to guarantee the correct number of activations of the deferrable appliances. The constraints are imposed in order to achieve the cheapest solution that considers both the consumption patterns and comfort requirements defined by the user. Household owners usually turn on the dishwasher after the lunch and/or dinner, activate their washing machine during the dawn, and so on. This kind of behaviour allows the algorithms to be personalized according to a timeframe of operation and user's consumption patterns. As for comfort requirements, thermal appliances are controlled by temperature, which allows the setting of a maximum and minimum temperature limits specified by the user. If any of these limits are exceeded, the algorithm apply a penalization. For instance, an activation of the AC must be penalized if the temperature is below the minimum or above the maximum limit.

$$\min S(x) = TC + \lambda_\theta + \lambda_{PL} + \lambda_D \quad (10)$$

- TC , total cost - equals to the total power consumed by the appliances multiplied by the respective value of the price tariff.
- λ_θ , penalization for the temperatures limits - if the temperature is outside the lower or upper limit, equals to the sum of all the surpluses between the respective temperature and limit.

- λ_{PL} , power cap penalization - if the power being consumed by all the appliances is greater than the power limit, equals to the difference between both values.
- λ_D , penalization to ensure the correct number of activations for deferrable appliances - if the total number of activations is not equal to one in each timeframe of operation or the appliance is operating outside the time limits, equals to the sum of the total excess. This penalization is only necessary for the CE method due to the nature of this heuristic.

The general idea for this formulation is to square all the penalizations that will converge to zero - namely the ones related to the constraints -, while the total cost, that is expected to never be zero, follow a linear behaviour. Thus, when all the restrictions are verified, only the linear function being minimized counts for the performance. Notice that the sub-function λ_{PL} is only applied when the power limit is considered and λ_D when using the CE Method. Furthermore, the penalizations are determined with Eq.11, where n is defined according to the method being applied and pe represents the value that results from the constraint.

$$\lambda_{pe} = n \cdot (1 + pe)^2 \quad (11)$$

Contrarily to what happens with the deterministic approach, the maximization of PV self-consumption in both heuristic methods is not achieved directly through a specific objective function, but rather indirectly through the goal of minimizing electricity costs, *i.e.*, by increasing the PV self-consumption, there will be less power being consumed from the electric grid, and consequently the energy costs will be minimized. This means that if the appliance's operation costs for a certain period without PV generation are cheaper than in a period with PV production, the algorithm will choose the first option. The remuneration for PV production injected into the grid is also considered, by subtracting from the final cost the product between the PV energy not used and the remuneration price.

Since the penalizations used to obtain the sub-functions of Eq.10 are determined separately and differently, the min-max method is applied to normalize all the penalties considered. This procedure eases the adjustment of the weights used to obtain the performances. In the case of the sub-functions regarding deferrable and thermal appliances, each penalization is also divided by the total number of the respective type of appliance in order to consider all equally, regardless the total number of devices included, and within a fixed range. For example, if there are only two different values for a certain penalty in all the samples and the range is [0-100], the minor takes the value 0 and the other the value 100. In this way, it is easier for the algorithm to choose between samples and the impact of the normalization starts to increase as the values begin to get closer.

5.2.1 Genetic Algorithm: Genetic algorithm (GA) is a probabilistic search algorithm based on the procedure of natural selection and genetics (Darwin selection). Its fundamental characteristics are based on the principles of survival of the fittest and adaptation to the environment. The GA in this article was specifically designed to minimize the electricity bill of user in their households, suggesting an optimal solution for the activation of some devices.

1. Initializing strategy

In order to initialize the evolution process of the GA, an initial population is chosen randomly. Each individual in the population contains a list with all the appliances defined in the beginning and the fitness value that evaluates the performance of each. In fig. 1 is an example of an individual structure with three different appliances.

Fig. 1: Example of individual structure.

2. Parents selection strategy

Having the initial population parents selection strategy decides on how to choose the parents of the next generation. All the individuals of the population are chosen as parents. There's no elitism preferences in this selection. The first parent is selected by order of the list and the second one is picked randomly and can't be equal to the other parent.

3. Genetic operators

The genetic operators are used to produce new individuals (offspring). Since this problem presents two categories of devices, shiftable and thermal, it was necessary to adapt the operators to each one.

Shiftable appliances only have one operator: mutation. The process begins by finding a new period of the day (one day is composed by 96 periods of 15 min.) and change the initial solution to another one that starts in the new point achieved.

Thermal appliances can suffer from crossover and/or mutation. Crossover operator starts by calculating crossover point (cxpoint) randomly and then two offspring are created. The first keeps parent one genetic part until the cxpoint and the rest from the second parent. The other is the contrary. Mutation in the case of the thermal appliances, chooses random points and turns them to the opposite signal, if it's on turn off and if it's off turn on.

4. New individuals selection

Selection has to be balanced: too strict selection reduces diversity and too weak selection will result in a too slow evolution. To prevent these problems, diverse selection methods are available, such as, roulette wheel, elitism, rank selection and tournament selection. In this optimization problem, two methods were used, elitism selection to choose a percentage of the fittest individuals and tournament selection to pick remain individuals. This hybrid selection is helpful to maintain the diversity between the individuals.

As this process is iterated, successive generations progress and by consequence, the average fitness tends to decrease until some stopping criterion is reached. In this problem, it was chosen to calculate the fitness value based on the minimization of the electricity expenditure in the household(s). That's why the fitness function tends to decrease.

5.2.2 Cross-Entropy Method: The CE is a heuristic that provides a simple, efficient and general method to deal with complex estimation and optimization problems. The CE method was first proposed by Rubinstein [27] as an adaptive Importance Sampling (IS) procedure for the estimation of rare-event probabilities, that uses the Kullback-Leibler divergence as a measure of similarity between sampling distributions. Later, a variation introduced to the Rubinstein formulation allowed the translation of rare-event estimation in an optimization heuristic, by associating the optimization problem in Eq.12 with the estimation of a probability $l = P(S(X) \leq \gamma)$, where γ is close to the unknown γ^* and x is a random variable parameterized by a finite-dimensional real vector v and with some density function $f(\cdot; v)$ on \mathcal{X} . [38]

Fig. 2: GA Algorithm Steps

$$S(x^*) = \gamma^* = \min_{x \in X} S(x) \quad (12)$$

Considering that l is a rare-event probability, it is possible to use a multi-level CE estimation approach to find an IS distribution that concentrates all its mass in a neighbourhood of the point \mathbf{x}^* . Sampling from such a distribution will thus produce optimal or near-optimal states. In contrast to the rare-event simulation, the final level $\gamma = \gamma^*$ is generally not known in advance. Nevertheless, the CE method for optimization produces a sequence of levels $\hat{\gamma}_t$ and reference parameters \hat{v}_t such that ideally the former tends to the optimal γ^* and the latter to the optimal reference vector v^* corresponding to the point mass at \mathbf{x}^* .

The energy consumption scheduling is formulated as a discrete multi-stochastic minimization problem with a finite state space represented by binary vectors. The final result is a binary vector, that indicates the time(s) that the device is going to be activated during the next day. This is achieved iteratively, following the structure presented in Fig. 3, where:

1. Set the initial parameters

Fig. 3: Simplified CE method for optimization

- N , number of random samples - affects directly the convergence speed and search range of the algorithm. To improve efficiency, this value can be adjusted according to the number of appliances being considered.
- ϱ , rarity parameter - to determine the number of elite samples ($N^e = \lfloor \varrho N \rfloor$) applied in the update of the probability \hat{v}_{t-1} .
- α , smoothing parameter - to soften the update of the probability \hat{v}_{t-1} to \hat{v}_t over iterations.
- $\hat{v}_0 = (1/2, \dots, 1/2)$, initial vector of probabilities - all states of the binary vector $\{0; 1\}$ start with the same probability of being generated.
- ϵ , stopping criterion error.

2. Random sample generation

A random number generator is set in order to draw samples from a set of parametric densities adequate to the problem. Given that only discrete variables are considered, the sampling distribution is based on the multivariate Bernoulli density:

$$f(x, v) = \prod_{j=1}^{j=n} v_j^{x_j} (1 - v_j)^{1-x_j}, \text{ for } x \in \{0, 1\} \quad (13)$$

, where n is the number of binary variables per sample. This procedure is made individually for each appliance, *i.e.*, each appliance has its own N independent random samples (X_1, \dots, X_N) .

3. Calculate performance for all N samples

The performances are determined using the function presented in 10. The number of performances being calculated in each t iteration is equal to N , *i.e.*, a single performance per k sample.

4. Order performances to obtain limit γ

For minimization problems, the performances are ordered from largest to smallest: $S(0) \geq \dots \geq S(N-1)$ and the limit ($\hat{\gamma}_t$) being estimated is the $(1 - \varrho)$ -quantile of the performances: $\hat{\gamma}_t = S_{(N - N^e - 1)}$. In this step, the goal is to obtain the limit $\hat{\gamma}_t$ that represents the last/worst performance to be considered. Moreover, the range of performances is directly

affected by N^e , which itself depends directly on ϱ .

5. Update probabilities \hat{v}_{t-1}

The update from \hat{v}_{t-1} to \hat{v}_t is made with the same set of samples (X_0, \dots, X_{N-1}) used to calculate the performances in the t iteration. The solution for the stochastic problem in each iteration is given by:

$$v_{t,j} = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} I_{\{S_k \leq \gamma_t\}} \cdot X_{k,j}}{\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} I_{\{S_k \leq \gamma_t\}}}, \quad j = 0, \dots, (n1) \quad (14)$$

, where n is the number of binary components of each sample and $X_{K,j}$ is the j -th component of the k -th random binary vector X . Notice that I is an indicator that takes the value 1 if the performance of the k -th sample satisfies the condition, and the value 0 if the opposite. Since the value of $X_{k,j}$ will always be in the interval $\{0;1\}$, the probability $\hat{v}_{k,j}$ is easily translated to a ratio between the number of times that the j -th component appears in the elite performances and the total number of elite performances being considered in the problem. After the probability is updated, the smoothing parameter (α) can be applied if necessary:

$$\hat{v}_t = \alpha \cdot \hat{v}_t + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \hat{v}_{t-1} \quad (15)$$

The solution for the problem in each iteration is v_t , that represents the sample with the best performance according to the objective function.

6. Stopping criterion

The algorithm only stops when the sampling distribution has degenerated enough or a maximum number of iterations is reached. For example, when $\hat{v}_{t,j}$ differ less than some small $\epsilon > 0$ from the $\{\hat{v}_{t-1,j}\}$. Hence, the difference between probabilities for each iteration is obtained by:

$$d_t = \max_{0 \leq j \leq (n-1)} \{ \min \{ \hat{v}_{t,j}, (1 - \hat{v}_{t,j}) \} \} \leq \epsilon \quad (16)$$

This means that the algorithm only stops if all the probabilities in the vector \hat{v}_t are equal or bigger than $(1 - \epsilon)$, or are equal or smaller than $(0 + \epsilon)$. If the criterion is not met, set $t = (t + 1)$ and return to step 2.

The evolution of the results can be divided in three main phases: (1) in the first iterations, the samples are severely penalized, and the costs have little significance when compared with the other penalties. This stage is when the algorithm slowly starts to generate samples towards the optimum region by excluding the ones that penalize the most; (2) when the quadratic functions begin to have the same order of magnitude as the linear functions, the algorithm starts to search the samples that minimize the costs in the objective function; (3) the algorithm produces samples around the optimal solution and the normalization starts to have greater impact in the selection of the samples. At this stage, the value of the performances starts to increase instead of decreasing because the normalization enlarges the difference between closer solutions. Therefore, the final result will not be measured by the performance of the sample, but rather by the total cost that results from the number of activations generated in that same sample.

6 Scenarios of Operation

The energy management methodology presented in the previous chapter was tested in a different set of scenarios that are likely to be found in typical daily-life applications. The formulation to solve the electricity consumption scheduling

was implemented in Python language for the heuristic case and C++ for the MILP.

These formulations includes the internal inputs related to the home domain and the external inputs received from service providers that are interested in shaping the energy demand of certain households. These settings were tested using real-data sets concerning two distinct countries, namely Portugal and Spain, in order to evaluate the algorithm with two different types of external data.

6.1 Usage Profiles

Several experiments have been carried out for the energy scheduler. In all scenarios, the appliances considered were the more likely ones to be found in households, clothes dryer (CD), dishwasher (DW), washing machine (WM), AC and EWH. The first three appliances are included in deferrable's group. This category includes all appliances that operate on a predefined cycle with a known duration and consumption. The other two belong to the category of thermal appliances where the only thing predefined is the power consumption.

For the creation of the scenarios, at least, duration and consumption of the appliances were estimated. Tracebase [39] data set is an appliance-level power consumption data set that was used to obtain appliances plug data. For that, more than one month of data were collected and each time the device activate the average power consumption and duration were kept. With all the statistics obtained before, a new general average power consumption and duration were achieved by calculating the mean value of each parameter. The values are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Deferrable appliances average characteristic values

	Clothes Dryer	Dishwasher	Washing Machine
Power[kW]	0.7	2	1
Cycle duration [h]	1	1.5	1

Table 2 presents the thermal appliances' characteristics, as well as the consumption patterns (baths information) and the comfort requirements (temperatures) that used in the study. Parameters of typical commercial appliances were considered. Realistic comfort temperatures as well as consumption patterns of the end-user were included. The EWH analysis comprised two hot water usages (38°C): 50 liters at 07:00 am and 17:00 pm.

Table 2 Thermal appliances average characteristic values

	Air Conditioner	Electric Water Heater
Power [kW]	3	2
Thermal capacity [kWh/°C]	2,72	0,117
Thermal resistance [°C/kWh]	4	1 / (9,42 E-4)
Coefficient of performance	3,6	3,6
Set point temperature [°C]	21	64,3
Number of baths	-	2
Baths Schedule [h]	-	7,17
Minimum temperature [°C]	17,5	45
Maximum temperature [°C]	24,2	80
Desired bath temperature[°C]	-	38

6.2 External Values

• Climate Conditions

To create a realistic scenario it is necessary to consider the ambient temperature variations when developing the thermal modelling. Obviously, the activation of the air conditioning

and even the heating of water differ regarding the external thermal conditions. Therefore, it was used different summer and winter temperatures of the two countries. The temperatures chosen for Portugal correspond to a typical summer / winter day in a hot Mediterranean climate in Alentejo (southern Portugal). In this region temperatures can reach 45 °C in summer and fall to a maximum of 11/12 in winter. In Spain as weather can be quite different depending on the region, for this analysis were chosen the temperatures of Coruña region with a cold Semi-Arid climate.

• Energy Prices

Dynamic pricing is a pricing strategy in which businesses set highly flexible prices for products or services based on current market demands.

In case of electricity pricing, dynamics prices are becoming more attractive due to its ability to influence consumption behaviour of customers. Households consumption patterns can be adjusted attended electricity prices. Most of the customers use large electric load at the same time, peak load, however this could be reduced if the consumer had information that in another time he has savings.

Different energy prices were assumed regarding different countries. For the Spanish case is considered a particular type of dynamic pricing referred to as the day-ahead hourly pricing [40]. This spanish tariff has roughly 12 millions of customers, it is calculated for each day (hourly) and the prices are published at 8:15pm of the previous day.

For the Portuguese case a bi-hourly TOU tariff [41] is used. In this case, workdays, Saturdays and Sundays are treated separately and different time-of-day periods are defined. In this framework, electricity supply tariffs can present two different energy prices (accordingly with the tariff period and, consequently, with different time schedules in each type of day). The PV remuneration price used was 0.045€, based on the average Portuguese values.

• Photovoltaic Production

In Portugal, the policy that is being implemented is to promote instantaneous consumption. For instance, for small PV installations announces lower remuneration for PV energy fed into the grid in comparison with the retailing energy price, thus ending the high feed-in tariffs that were in use. This makes self-consumption always more profitable than injecting PV generation into the grid. However, daily profiles of PV generation are usually not correlated with the consumption, namely in the residential sector, since a significant part of the population is not at home during daylight hours. Therefore, some form of flexible consumption is required at the local level so that it can be shifted to the periods when PV generation is higher.

In order to validate the methodology that enables the scheduling with PV and due it variation by season, two different types of data were collected for summer and winter to provide valid results.

7 Results and Discussion

The scenarios discussed in this sector uses the data presented in the previous sectors. Eight scenarios were tested, four for each country, to be possible to evaluate the savings and profile behaviour when the tariff system, the season of the year and the type of optimization are changed:

- Portugal Summer RC - Residential house considering bi-hourly energy prices and Warm Mediterranean climate (Alentejo) in the Summer.
- Portugal Summer PV - Residential house considering PV production and Warm Mediterranean climate (Alentejo) in the Summer

- Portugal Winter RC - Residential house considering bi-hourly energy prices and Warm Mediterranean climate (Alentejo) in the Winter
- Portugal Winter PV - Residential house considering bi-hourly energy prices and Warm Mediterranean climate (Alentejo) in the Winter
- Spain Summer RC - Residential house considering bi-hourly energy prices and cold Semi-Arid climate (Coruna) in the Summer.
- Spain Summer PV - Residential house considering PV production and cold Semi-Arid climate (Coruna) in the Summer
- Spain Winter RC - Residential house considering bi-hourly energy prices and cold Semi-Arid climate (Coruna) in the Winter
- Spain Winter PV - Residential house considering bi-hourly energy prices and cold Semi-Arid climate (Coruna) in the Winter

The following subsections begin by presenting an example of a optimal schedule and the optimal and sub optimal solutions for each scenario provided by the CPLEX and SCIP solver for the deterministic case. Then an analysis of the heuristic algorithms performance is presented that includes the day ahead total cost, average running time and the total consumption optimized.

Finally, a summary of all results is showed. It is presented the savings of each method regarding the baseline, as well as the additional cost over the optimal solution.

7.1 Mixed Integer Linear Programming

The presented MILP formulation was implemented in the C++ language to allow the performance-oriented implementation. To solve the optimization problem, two different solvers were used, CPLEX and SCIP.

Despite producing faster results, the cplex solver has the problem that cannot be used in platforms like raspberry PI, where the HEMS is installed. Therefore, SCIP was also used as a workaround. In any case, the results of the CPLEX solver are presented as a benchmark to compare other solvers and methods since the probability of reaching the optimum is greater with CPLEX. Moreover, as the SCIP has a slower performance, it was used with a gap of 5 % to reach useful results in a reliable time.

The results of these simulations were the optimized cost of equipment scheduling for the next day. This specific problem has 576 integer variables for the first objective function and 768 (576 binary, 192 continuous) for the second objective function and both have 580 (linear) constraints. An example of this output for the next day is presented in the Figure 4 where a optimized schedule for the third spanish case is presented.

It is illustrated that all the consumption is shifted to the hours when the energy prices are lower and all the deferrable appliances comply with the deadline constraints. AC and EWH are activated more often at lower prices periods to maintain the required temperature during the time of day when prices are higher.

However, this type of scheduling can cause problems due the overload at the lowest price period. This can activate the protection systems when there are power limits. Therefore, a restriction of 4.6 kW was added to avoid this problem and it is demonstrated in Figure 5.

7.1.1 CPLEX vs SCIP: To obtain the optimal result, that can be achieved with the MILP formulation, the eight scenarios were solved with the CPLEX. However, for the eight tested scenarios was not possible to obtain the optimal value in the required time for two cases – the third and fourth scenario of the Portuguese case. They both quickly reached a 1% gap, however, it takes weeks to reach a 0% gap, thus here is

Fig. 4: Produced schedule for the spanish scenario

Fig. 5: Produced schedule for the spanish scenario with power cap limitation

only presented the best achieved value for these two specific scenarios.

In order to understand how much the user can save with this type of algorithms produced by the HEMS, a calculation of how much can be saved is made for each scenario considering the expenses that would have if the devices were activated in normal hours (a baseline scenario). For example, the deferrable appliances are considered to be activated in periods where the average LV consumption is higher, usually at dinner time. And for AC and EWH the activation is considered using the thermal behaviour without optimization to keep the temperature limits.

The Table 3 shows the final results of how much the user can save per day in each scenario if he accepts the automatic activation for all equipment.

Table 3 Baseline Savings

Country Savings (€)	Scenarios			
	Summer RC	Summer PV	Winter RC	Winter pv
Portugal	2.25	2.39	2.40	2.30
Spain	1.19	0.75	1.57	2.47

These daily results presents the maximum value that is possible to save per day with HEMS installed in the household. Obviously, these values are regarding the physical and external conditions described and for a specific day that has the necessity to connect all devices. These savings can change depending on the need to use household appliances and the ability to control them remotely.

For the SCIP solver, a 5 minutes limit running time period was used (considered viable for the end user to wait). It is illustrated both in Figure 6 (Portugal) and in Figure 7 (Spain) that final values obtained with the SCIP solver do not demonstrated a great difference CPLEX. In fact, this difference translated into prices is practically irrelevant. For instance, the last Spanish case where the loss is higher, the expense translates into 0.009 € in one day. This loss compared with a saving of € 2.47 per day can be considered a residual value that does not make much difference to the final user.

7.2 Heuristics

A crude Monte Carlo method is applied to analyze the behaviour of the heuristics (GA and CE) in terms of achieving the optimal result. For that purpose, 100 simulations of each scenario are performed, with the seeds for the random generation fixed in order to track the different results in each simulation. Both heuristics are compared in terms of total cost of operation, total running time of the simulations and total electricity consumption. For a detailed analysis, the

Fig. 6: MILP results for the Portuguese scenarios

Fig. 7: MILP results for the Spanish scenarios

costs and consumption for each period of 15 min were also considered. However, these last ones demonstrate to be less relevant, since the variety of values didn't allow to take any conclusion.

Table 4 Portugal - Monte Carlo average values

Portugal	Parameters	Cross-Entropy	Genetic Algorithm
Summer RC	Total daily cost (€)	4.37	4.87
	Total running time (min)	8.68	5.57
	Total daily consumption (kWh)	27.48	30.48
Summer PV	Total daily cost (€)	2.56	3.03
	Total running time (min)	9.22	5.81
	Total daily consumption (kWh)	27.48	28.97
Winter RC	Total daily cost (€)	4.23	4.71
	Total running time (min)	9.17	6.25
	Total daily consumption (kWh)	31.23	31.98
Winter PV	Total daily cost (€)	4.10	4.60
	Total running time (min)	10.96	6.13
	Total daily consumption (kWh)	31.23	31.98

Table 5 Spain - Monte Carlo average values

Spain	Parameters	Cross-Entropy	Genetic Algorithm
Summer RC	Total daily cost (€)	1.09	1.12
	Total running time (min)	6.91	4.03
	Total daily consumption (kWh)	13.73	14.97
Summer PV	Total daily cost (€)	0.12	0.28
	Total running time (min)	7.75	4.13
	Total daily consumption (kWh)	14.73	15.478
Winter RC	Total daily cost (€)	2.44	2.58
	Total running time (min)	9.06	5.41
	Total daily consumption (kWh)	31.23	31.98
Winter PV	Total daily cost (€)	1.53	1.63
	Total running time (min)	10.35	5.47
	Total daily consumption (kWh)	31.98	31.98

As can be seen in tables 4 and 5, the averages of the total daily electricity consumption are very similar in both heuristics, but the average total daily cost has shown better results with CE. Usually, GA has higher costs because the AC is activated more times or in a period where the price is higher. This means that GA could be stuck in a local optimum.

Analyzing the total running time, GA shows faster convergence than the CE algorithm. However, CE algorithm, despite taking approximately ten minutes to perform a scenario with at least five appliances, it gives fast and optimal results in a matter of a few minutes or even seconds when considering less appliances, namely if all are deferrable. And, the increase of the running times is mainly related to the thermal appliances, since it is necessary to obtain the temperatures for each period, of each sample, in each iteration, with the thermal equations. Furthermore, thermal appliances also have a larger range for possible activations than the deferrable ones, due to the type of constraints associated (maintain temperature inside limits). Another factor that tampers with the running time is the type of tariff being used. With more dynamic tariffs, such as the one used in the Spanish cases, the algorithm converges faster and usually with much less probability of being penalized.

Regarding the average daily consumption, both Portugal and Spain during winter, presents quite identical results. In the summer, however, Portugal has higher daily consumption than Spain because its summer temperatures are higher and consequently the AC is activated more times. Moreover, as can be perceived in the Spanish scenarios, the average of the total daily consumption can vary slightly between scenarios with and without the PV. This difference is only caused by the thermal appliances - since the deferrable ones have a predefined number of operations -, that are activated with zero or near zero cost during periods with higher PV production, even if the temperature is within the fixed limits.

7.3 Comparison

To understand the advantages of choosing deterministic or non-deterministic methods, it is important to compare the algorithms running time as well as the price increase introduced by the heuristic variation. In the Table 6 are the summary average time of all solvers. SCIP is not considered since it has always exceeded the 5-minute limit (with the exception of the three scenarios mentioned before).

As expected, from the previous subsections, the average values of running time from CPLEX are quite exaggerated, explaining the necessity to limit the gap for the raspberry PI. The heuristics are much faster, within a 10mn period, that would not affect the end user.

Finally, to compare the performance of each algorithm is illustrated in Figures 8 and 9 the loss that each algorithm can

Table 6 Average running time

	MILP (CPLEX)	Genetic Algorithm	Cross-Entropy method
Average time (min)	63	2	9

present when it is compared with the optimal solution from CPLEX.

Fig. 9: Spain - Losses of the methods comparing to CPLEX

The results present some similarities. SCIP losses have an average of 0.016€ for all scenarios, making it almost not visible on the figures. In the second scenario both heuristics presented worst results. However, in average none of the heuristics have losses higher than 0.10€ per day.

All algorithms present good results for HEMS integration and proved that can be used in real life scenarios. Although some savings are lost with the heuristics, these values are residual to the user and do not make that much difference in the total achieved savings.

8 Conclusion

Nowadays, environmental issues are a critical topic discussed all over the world. HEMS are used to reduce the environmental problems helping households in their daily electrical consumption's. The presented paper shows the important role of the HEMS in the reduction of the electricity bill and consequently energy consumption.

The formulation for the scheduling of the electricity consumption in a building was detailed in this work, where a single objective function was developed, for the non-deterministic case, to be used in the general structure. Although the mathematical formulation has some complexity associated to it, the convergence of the algorithm to optimal or sub-optimal results is assured.

The formulation of the shiftable appliances poses some challenges, namely to guarantee that the appliance is activated inside pre-defined timeframes. Conversely, the formulation for the thermal appliances is simplified with the use of the PLBMs.

It is possible to conclude from Section 7 that all algorithms can present viable results for HEMS integration and can be used in real life scenarios. Although some savings are lost with the heuristics, these values are residual to the user and do not make that much difference in the total savings that can be achieved.

Heuristics also have the advantage that they can be adapted and improved for specific cases. In fact, the structure of the algorithm to obtain the single objective function is flexible enough to be changed, it is possible to add, remove or alter the steps in order to enhance its performance. In the same way that the number of samples is adjusted in this work according to the number of appliances to reduce the running time, other parameters could be also adjusted to improve time and performance. For instance, an auto-adaptive smoothing parameter, mainly to be applied in the generation of the random samples of the thermal appliances.

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